

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Health care outcomes due to incidents of burnout in Asia: A literature review

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Abstract

Introduction: Stress is a part of life that is considered one of the great pandemics of the 21st century. At work, stress can affect health, personal well-being and job satisfaction, and in severe cases can trigger burnout syndrome. Factors that cause burnout including personal factors, workload excessive, and the quality of the work environment that do not support.

Methods: This research uses literature study design from an international database, namely PubMed with the keywords used "burnout", "health workers", and "cross sectional".

Result and Discussion: There have been 1942 journals in the last 10 years. After that, the year of publication and language screening were carried out in 399 journals, then the researchers identified screening titles, abstracts, and complete copies of 46 journals and selected accordingly with the inclusion criteria so that 13 articles will be reviewed in this literature review.

Conclusion: It was found that burnout has a negative impact on health services as well as on the quality of life of health workers.

Keywords: Burnout; Health Workers; Outcome; Asia

1. Introduction

Burn-out is a negative condition characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization/cynicism, and dissatisfaction with own performance or low self-achievement. Emotional exhaustion is considered as initial or central symptom that expresses itself as emotional exhaustion or exhaustion due to work combined with a lack of energy and feeling tired or exhausted in the morning before it starts working. Cynicism or depersonalization is an advanced symptom that develops under excessive work stress and prolonged which describes a callous, distant reaction with bitterness to the work condition, blame, and cynicism towards their co-workers and relatives. Depersonalization is also possible understood as a protective mechanism in the incidence of advanced burnout. Dissatisfaction with performance describes feelings of failure in terms of performance at work and of not being able to achieve anything with own abilities and efforts. Factors that contribute to burn-out include personal factors, excessive workload, and the quality of the work environment that are not supportive [1, 2].

Related studies have been carried out on health care professionals with a prevalence of burn-out syndrome in gastroenterology experts in the United States reached 32-63% who showed symptoms of emotional exhaustion [3], stroke neurologists and non-stroke neurologists 44.6% of whom have burnout syndrome [4]. In addition, 50% of anesthesiologists also reported burnout [5]. Not only health workers, medicine student's are also at risk of developing

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depression due to long study periods and lack of sleep. This can reduce the quality of life and lead to increased rates of depression which impacts on physical health, mental and emotional, and can harm academic achievement [6]. Stress is a condition experienced by a person as a result of an increased burden of thought. Psychosocial stressors also impact changes in the performance of the hypothalamus and the production of glucocorticoids and catecholamines thereby causing decreased immunity [7]. Psychodynamics and culture influence behavior in response to distress and produce a variable clinical picture of depression [8]. Sleep disturbance is one of the features depressive disorder. As many as 50-90% of depressed patients complain of sleep disturbances [9]. Plus, stress contributes to psychological stress and burnout, which can contribute to personal consequences and professionals, including an increase in the rate of medical errors, malpractice lawsuits, to an increase possibility of suicide [10]. This occurs because psychosocial stress increases the activity of the HPA axis characterized by increased CRH in the cerebrospinal fluid. CRH increases ACTH hormone hyper secretion and increased hypercortisolemia. Cortisol functions to maintain life by regulating sleep, appetite, kidney function, and the immune system. Elevated cortisol levels stimulate the mechanism negative feedback loops such as the hypothalamus suppressing CRH secretion. Then it sends a message to the pituitary to decrease ACTH production and be relayed back to the adrenals to reduce cortisol production. However, under conditions of chronic stress, the auto regulation system or negative feedback function does not work. The HPA axis causes depression during psychosocial stress and is at greater risk for injury self-esteem, suicidal ideas, or behavior [11]. The low acceptance against depression as a disease is thought to be the cause of the less attention and stigmatization of sufferers, which ultimately leads to misdiagnosis and inappropriate strategies for treatment [12].

2. Material and methods

This study uses a review article research design with a type of literature review. The focus of this literature review is looking at the relationship between burnout and the influence on the environment around the scope of the profession health. Articles reviewed are limited to articles with research sample cross sectional study to know the relationship between burnout and the impact that may arise, the population of Professions in the Field Health in ASIA, excluding covid-19, published articles in 2022 in English and Indonesian, as well as original articles and available in full text form. Article search using electronics data bases namely PubMed with English keywords (“Burnout”, “Heath Worker”, “Cross Sectional”).

3. Results and discussion

The results of a literature search were 1942 journals in the last 10 years. After that, filtering is done year of publication and language obtained as many as 399 journals, then the researcher conducted screening identification titles, abstracts, and complete copies of 46 journals and selection according to the inclusion criteria so that it got 13 articles that will be reviewed in this literature review. Once done screening finally, there are 13 literary works that fit to the author's criteria.

The selected articles are research articles that make observations to determine the factors that affect burnout in health workers and the results obtained due to burnout incidents. Articles that were obtained located in health service locations originating from various countries in Asia, including Iran, Korea, Israel, Oman, Saudi, Turkey, Taiwan, China and produced 13 articles that proved that the incidence of burnout of health workers has a negative impact on health services and quality of life of health workers.

Burnout occurs when a person is faced with an emotionally demanding work situation for long periods of time, which results in physical and emotional exhaustion clinical symptoms such as cognitive impairment, sleep disturbance, and functional impairment [13]. Lack of resources, unclear rules, unnecessary missions, burnout, physical and emotional stress and Cognitive cause burnout syndrome [14]. According to the findings of the research journal review conducted by Tsou [15] on the medical profession in China, burnout causes insomnia and sleep deprivation, which does irregular exercise, unhealthy eating habits that increase the risk of chronic disease to death. Incidence of burnout has a negative impact on patient health as well as cause low level patient satisfaction during visits [16; 17; 18; 13; 19; 20]. In addition, on the findings of a research journal review that conducted by Alenezi [18] and Tsai [21] stated burnout manifests in anxiety and depression as well associated with well-being and poor performance. Neuroticism or unstable emotions are risk factors for depression [20]. Previous research has consistently found job characteristics the disadvantages, such as high workload, low staffing levels, long shifts, low control self-esteem, low schedule flexibility, time pressure, work and psychological demands, low various task, role conflict, low autonomy, negative relationship among health workers, poor support, poor leadership, negative team relations, and job insecurity [22].

Work resources are supporting factors related to environmental, social, and aspects organization, including autonomy and social support that function in achieving work targets, reduce job demands, as well as encourage the growth and development of employees [22]. In addition, according to the findings a review of research journals conducted by Wang [20] stated a statistically significant correlation between the quality of teamwork and burnout of health workers shows the quality of teamwork and burnout are correlated canonically. The surge in the quality of team work led to less emotional exhaustion and depersonalization while increasing professional achievement. Self-realization needs involve goals, potency, personal satisfaction, personal achievement (PA), and scientific discovery. Self-realization is considered as a motivation that can regulate human behavior and the level of development to be achieved [5]. Positive feedback accompanied by high job acceptance will make commitment and work appreciation higher, deep realizing the value of life [23].

Research from See [24] states that among Asian ICU physicians and nurses, both experience high levels of burnout, namely 50.3% (doctors) and 52.0% (nurses) respectively. Burnout experienced by Asian ICU physicians and nurses are also related to stress and the possibility of depression. Among nurses, burnout causes a decrease in suitability and readiness to carry out treatment according to existing SOPs, which can lead to poor treatment outcomes for patients. There are several factors that can increase and decrease burnout levels. Declining levels of burnout are associated with religiosity, years of work in the current department, shift work, better balance between work and life and stay-home night calls, while factors that increase are working days per month and levels of education (bachelor's degree). Reviewing the high level of burnout, it is necessary to have interventions that focus on reducing workload and promoting balance between life. Such changes can be made at the organizational level. In addition, it is also important to carry out screening for burnout for level workers.

4. Conclusion

The discussion of the article above leads to the conclusion that the incidence of burnout in health of workers has a negative impact on health services and quality of life. Burnouts happen when a person is exposed to an emotionally demanding work situation over a long period of time. Burnout incidents can also cause insomnia and lack of sleep, does irregular exercise, habits in eating an unhealthy diet that increases the risk of chronic disease to death. Resource work is a supporting factor related to environmental, social, and organizational aspects. Besides that, the quality of teamwork leads to reduce emotional exhaustion and depersonalization and also increase professional achievement. Self-realization is considered as a motivation that can regulate human behavior and level of development to be achieved.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare there is no conflict of interest in this study.

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